

THE POSTHUMOUS FATE OF JESUS BODY: BETWEEN CHRISTIAN TRADITION AND HISTORY

Jerzy Adam Kowalski, Ph.D.

Centre for the Theory of Myth and Ritual, Institute of Sex Research, Warsaw, Poland
e-mail: j.kowalski@ibs.opole.pl

Abstract. *The author uses the probabilistic-historical method as a part of the critical-historical approach to consider diverse possible variants of events related to the burial of Jesus. Given the Jewish funeral customs and the social status of Jesus' family, the most likely variant was that Jesus' body would have been finally buried in the family tomb, if there had been such a one nearby. Since Jesus' father was from Bethlehem, near Jerusalem, it is possible that this is where such a tomb was located and so Jesus' remains were moved there for his final rest. Many additional circumstances indicate such a possibility, including various passages of the gospels, historical data on those times, as well as the structural and social diversity of the first Christian community.*

Keywords: *historicity of Jesus, empty tomb, Jesus resurrection, Jesus family, critical-historical method*

One of the biggest riddles in the study of Jesus' historicity is the posthumous fate of his body. A huge number of publications has already been devoted to this issue. Here we look at this issue, starting from the assumption that the messages retained by the Christian tradition have become a kind of mythology and, as such, can be a source for a historical reconstruction of events only by means of an appropriate reinterpretation. The method that serves such a reinterpretation is generally called the critical-historical method; in this paper, we will use a variant of this method, which could be described as the probabilistic-historical method because it is based on estimating the historical probability of various possible versions of events.

In the case of death by crucifixion practiced by ancient Romans, the body of a deceased convict could be removed in three ways: (i) leaving the body on the cross until the remains are decayed; (ii) throwing villains into an unmarked mass grave; (iii) traditional burial. In the case of Jesus, it seems that the most justified position is occupied by those researchers who advocate the

third version (see, i.a., Craig, 2014, 147; Dunn, 2002; Evans, 2009; Lowder, 2005; Robinson, 1973). In the Christian tradition and critical-historical literature, the most strongly grounded is the thesis that it was Joseph of Arimathea who took the body of the deceased Jesus and buried it in a rock tomb near Golgotha, which might have belonged to Joseph himself (see, i.a., Allison, 2005, 352-363; R. E. Brown, 1994, 1241; Craig, 2014; Dunn, 2003; Lowder, 2005; O'Collins & Kendall, 1994).

However, the most important challenge for anyone who, employing the principles of rational reasoning, wishes to understand what happened shortly after Jesus was crucified, is to find an explanation for discovering an empty place where the body of the deceased had been entombed. The very existence of this fact is found as very probable by most researchers (see, e.g., Craig, 1985, 2014; Dunn, 2003; Habermas, 2004; McDonald, 2013). Habermas (as cited by Licona, 2008, 324) estimates that nearly 3/4 of the researchers writing on this subject since 1975 advocate the historical credibility of this fact. Various attempts have been made to explain the mystery of the empty tomb. Most researchers, to a greater or lesser extent, give faith to the reports on the real coming into being of Jesus' resurrection with the participation of supernatural forces (Licona, 2008, 325). Only a small number of researchers support naturalistic and rationalist explanations, and these are, i.a.: Allison (2005), Bostock (1994), Carnley (1987), Ehrman (1999), Fisher (1999), Grant (1977), Vermes (2008). Meanwhile, it seems that the latter are the only explanations that we can accept on the ground of—strictly understood—science. It is that if someone manages to show irrefutably the real existence of phenomena considered today as supernatural, then at the same time they will become natural phenomena and will be included in the subject of scientific research. One of the most credible explanations for the mystery of the empty tomb within the naturalistic paradigm seems to be the assumption that Jesus' body was moved to a place other than the original burial site and finally buried there. We will take a closer look at this possibility.

As the earliest one, the suspicion occurred that it was the followers of Jesus who took (sometimes said "stole") the body of Jesus and buried it in another, unknown place. The appearance of such explications was reported yet by Matthew (27: 62-65, 28: 11-15). This version of events was upheld in modern times by, i.a., Holtzmann (1906) and Klausner (1925, 357). A quite similar concept is the hypothesis by R. E. Brown (1994, 1250), stating that Jesus' original resting place was only temporary and the intention was to move his body to another place. Carrier (2005) goes in the same direction, suggesting that eventually Jesus' corpse could have been transferred to the communal mass grave for criminals; this position is strongly supported by Lowder (2005). It seems, however, that the solution presented by Carrier would be quite a breakneck undertaking. The reason for it would be lack of time to complete the funeral rites on the day of Jesus death, that is on Friday

afternoon just before the Sabbath. However, a number of doubts arise here. Firstly, making an honorable burial—as it was recognized the burial in a family tomb (see Hachlili, 1988), and turning it two days later into a shameful burial in the tomb of condemned criminals seems a bizarre solution. Secondly, no one could ask Joseph to donate his own tomb for such purposes (which, additionally, would require special purification procedures afterwards); and thirdly, this version of events would certainly be known to the followers of Jesus, so they should not be surprised by the absence of Jesus' body in the tomb of Joseph of Arimathea. Therefore, instead of surprised women on Sunday morning (as agreeably described by Matthew 28: 1-8; Mark 16: 1-8; Luke 24: 1-12; John 20: 1-10), we should rather expect men to appear there (e.g. Joseph of Arimathea), as only men could complete the mourning rituals - supposedly incomplete before the Sabbath.

Recently, McDonald (2013, 447-448), listing all hypothetical possibilities of explaining the mystery of the empty tomb, mentioned the possibility that the tomb of Jesus' family might have been located nearby, and this is where his remains could eventually rest. However, the author immediately dismisses this theoretical possibility, recalling that Jesus came from Nazareth, which is much too far from Jerusalem to think about moving his body to the family tomb. But did McDonald exclude such possibilities too hastily?

To answer this question, we have to consider many factors. Let us start with customs and religious traditions of contemporary Jews regarding the burying of the dead. A lot of data on this subject is provided by Breytenbach (2012, 608; emphasis added):

*In Israelite tradition, all Jews had the right to be buried (Philo, Flacc. 61, 65). The desire was burial in peace (Sir 4: 14), men in the family tomb (1 Macc 9: 19; Jdt 8: 3; T. 12 Patr. passim) and wives with their husbands (Jdt 16: 23; Tob 4: 4; 14: 9, 12). [...] Upon the living, especially **the next of kin** (cf. Josephus, J.W. 5.568), fell the responsibility to bury the dead (Sir 38: 16), burials belonging to **the private sphere of the family** and not to the public cult. [...] The burial of strangers was a deed of piety (Tob 1: 17-19; 2: 4-8), the absence of someone to bury the dead (Wis 18: 12; 1 Macc 7: 17; 4 Macc 16: 11; Pss. Sol. 2:26) or the lack of a grave (Bel 31; Philo, Ios. 23-25; T. Job 40: 13) a sign of desolation and shame.*

Several other researchers also emphasize that Jewish tombs were family tombs and that only members of the same family in the male line and their wives or mothers could rest in them, and the obligation to arrange a funeral and perform appropriate funeral rituals belonged to male members of the nearest family (see, i.a., P. Brown, 2008, 42; Cohen-Matlofsky, 2013, 77-78; Hachlili, 1988; Magness, 2007; Marcus, 2004; Sanders, 1985, 253-255). Evans (2005) and Carrier (2005) emphasize that Jews treated their customary rights in this field as a sacred duty.

Taking into account the above circumstances, and especially the multigenerational

character of Jewish tombs and their strictly patriarchal character (emphasis on kinship in the male line), it seems that Jesus' family tomb should be sought not so much in the place where he lived or stayed, but in the place from where his immediate agnates came. And that place was probably Bethlehem in Judea.

Bethlehem is mentioned as the place of Jesus' birth by Matthew (2: 1-6) and Luke (2: 4), and it is mentioned enigmatically by John (7: 41-42). *The Proto-Gospel of James* (17: 8), a document from the 2nd century C.E., attributed by the tradition to James, Jesus' brother, repeats in part the narrative of Jesus' childhood from Luke's Gospel, but adds some completely new elements. Joseph and Mary were to be accompanied by Joseph's sons from his earlier marriage on their way from Nazareth to Bethlehem, and Jesus' birth was to take place in the desert some 3.5 kilometers north of Bethlehem. Around this place, in the 5th century C.E. there was built the "Kathisma of the Theotokos" in order to celebrate this event (cf. Shoemaker, 2001, 2003).

However, Bethlehem in Judea as the birthplace of Jesus is widely questioned in the literature (see, i.a. Borg, 1999, 179; R. E. Brown, 1977, 36; 1994, 513-516; Freed, 2004, 75-86; Meier, 1991, 214-216; Sanders, 1993, 85; Vermes, 2006, 22). Most often, researchers believe, as does, e.g., Dunn (2003, 345), that the indication of Bethlehem may be a derivative of the narrative that Jesus came from the lineage of King David, the king who just hailed from Bethlehem, and an attempt to adjust the Gospel stories to certain ancient biblical prophecies regarding the place of origin of the foretold new Jewish messiah. But is not such skepticism taken too far? The fact that a piece of information matches previous prophecies does not in itself prove that the information is false or true—otherwise no one who was actually born in Bethlehem could claim to be a messiah in those days because skeptics would always claim information about his birthplace as highly suspect, too fitting the prophecy. This reasoning can be reversed. Perhaps Christian writers did not attribute Jesus to Bethlehem as his place of birth, because they recognized him as the messiah, but vice versa—it was Jesus himself who felt selected in a special way because, among other things, he hailed from Bethlehem and from the royal family, and thus he fulfilled the premises of certain biblical prophecies. It should be remembered, as well, that the narratives about the birth of Jesus in the Gospels of Matthew and Luke were written sometime around 80-90 C.E. (cf. P. Brown, 2008; Ehrman, 1999), they, therefore, must have been in circulation for at least the decade preceding this event (that is AD 70-80). Meanwhile, people who knew Jesus well lived until quite recently, e.g. his brother James died somewhere between 62 and 69 CE (cf. Eddy & Boyd, 2007, 130), and the apostle Peter was executed in AD 67 (cf. Hamman, 1971). About 90 CE there certainly still lived close relatives of Jesus. According to a Church historian Eusebius of Caesarea, it was at this time that Emperor Domitian was to interrogate two grandsons of Judah, the brother of Jesus (cf. P.

Brown, 2008). In this situation, it seems unlikely that false information about the basic facts of Jesus' life would be disseminated because that would be very easily exposed. Yet, it is one thing to embellish accounts of secondary birth circumstances, and another to distort the most basic data.

But for our considerations, even more important than the place of Jesus' birth is the place of his father's origin—for it is the place where one should look for the location of the family tomb in the male line. Although it is difficult to be unambiguous here, the information is a bit more reliable. Joseph is mentioned as the father of Jesus by Luke (2: 46-51; 4:22) and John (1:45; 6:42), while Matthew (1:16) writes carefully about Joseph as the husband of Mary, the mother of Jesus; however, both Luke (3: 23-38) and Matthew (1: 1-17) include Joseph in their genealogy of Jesus. According to Matthew (2: 11-23), Joseph first lived in Bethlehem and thereafter he lived in Nazareth during Jesus' childhood, while in Luke (2: 4) we read „Joseph went up from Galilee, out of the city of Nazareth, into Judaea, to the city of David, which is called Bethlehem”, and it was supposed to be caused by the necessity to go to the place of birth for the census ordered at that time. Despite the partly contradictory information, both evangelists agree that Joseph was from Bethlehem. The above-mentioned information that Jesus' father was to come from the lineage of King David harmonizes quite well with this information.

We must also answer the question whether Jesus' family in the male line was wealthy enough to afford a tomb carved into the rock? As Crossan and Reed (2001, 245) note, the lower classes buried their dead in simple shallow graves or trenches, usually without any inscriptions or other costly additions. Kirby (2005, 244) adds that the tombs carved into the rock were expensive and, therefore, were accessible only to the middle and upper classes (see also Evans, 2005, 201). In such tombs, convicts were not usually buried, but there is evidence that this happened sometimes (Lowder, 2005, 266-267). So what was Jesus' social and property status? Some scholars believe that Jesus came from a prosperous rather than poor family (see, e.g., Cohen-Matlofsky, 2013, 82; Dunn, 2003, 313-320). Buchanan (1984, 240) strongly believes that Jesus came from a wealthy family, and Hollenbach (1982) even suspects that Jesus' family was a prominent one. Of course, this does not contradict the above-mentioned suggestion that the lineage of Jesus was descended from King David. There are also some additional arguments supporting the hypothesis about the relative prosperity of Jesus' family. Surely, a certain degree of wealth was required to afford a good education and good manners, which can be attributed to Jesus (cf. Dunn, 2003, 320). Also, certain material resources were needed to devote oneself to religious studies and meditation, and then to several years of traveling teaching—such an activity would be difficult to imagine in terms of everyday struggles for physical survival. Not without significance it may be also a rather ascetic lifestyle that Jesus led (Dunn, 2003, 313), and even such a significant detail as a rather comfortable

place where the last supper before his death took place—it was located in a prestigious part of Jerusalem between the palace of the high priest, the palace of Herod, and the statue of King David (cf. Pixner, 1990). Also, the information of Eusebius of Caesarea that two generations later the descendants of one of Jesus' brothers had acreage of 3.7 hectares of land (P. Brown, 2008), shows that despite the constant fragmentation of property as a result of the inheritance, the family of Jesus was quite wealthy. Finally, let us mention the Gospel story—though we do not know if it is true—about the rich garments of Jesus shared by the executioners (Luke 23:34; John 19: 23-25). In this entire context, it becomes highly probable that the male lineage of Jesus had a family rock-cut tomb.

If this tomb was situated in Bethlehem, the place of origin of at least Jesus' father, it becomes evident that if it were just possible to arrange Jesus' traditional burial, his body could not rest forever in a strange tomb and had to be moved to the right place. And let us recall that Bethlehem was only about 7 kilometers from then Jerusalem, and it was therefore less than two hours' walk. The body of Jesus could therefore be placed in the tomb of Joseph of Arimathea temporarily for the coming Sabbath, and could be easily transferred to the family tomb in Bethlehem after the Sabbath was over. Numerous Jewish sources testify that the transfer of a corpse from one grave to another was at the time a perfectly acceptable practice and in some cases even an expected one (see Carrier, 2005, footnotes 43, 44).

In this context, it is necessary to look in a completely new light at the participation of Joseph of Arimathea in the burial of Jesus. In the literature on the subject, three possibilities are usually adopted in this matter:

- Joseph was motivated by piety, that is Jewish religious commands regarding the burial of a fellow believer; so thinks, e.g., Carrier (2005, footnote 45), referring to Mark (15:43, 16:1);
- Joseph was a follower of Jesus, as, e.g., Craig (1989, 175) deems, believing the reports of Matthew (27: 57-59) and John (19: 38-40);
- Joseph fulfilled the Sanhedrin's will (their leadership) to provide the condemned man with a proper funeral; so thinks, e.g., Lowder (2005).

It should be noted, however, that neither the piety of Joseph of Arimathea, nor the command of the Sanhedrin, nor sympathy with the teachings of Jesus required to give his gens' tomb to someone—something difficult to imagine in the context of the customs of the time; these factors did not also rule out making up by Joseph a simple burial in a trench for Jesus. Therefore, quite another possibility seems more likely. Well, perhaps Joseph acted on behalf of Jesus' immediate family—either at their request or on his own initiative as a blood-related or related by affinity person. Only in this case, he could know that Jesus' final burial in his family tomb in nearby Bethlehem was

possible, and on the very day of his death it would suffice to temporarily lay the body elsewhere (e.g. in an empty tomb). Joseph's activity in the case was necessary because members of Jesus' immediate family were absent at the place of execution. The evangelists inform us quite unanimously about such absence (Dijkhuizen, 2011, 126). It is true that John (19: 25-27) is the only one to mention Jesus' mother as present at the execution of her son, but it seems unlikely and is probably a projection of the state of affairs expected by the evangelist. This fact, as we have already mentioned, is irrelevant anyway because under the Jewish law a woman was incapable of arranging a funeral for a deceased—only men could do it (Carrier, 2005, footnote 27).

However, it is highly probable that after Jesus' death, someone from his close family came to Jerusalem on the occasion of the Passover. In those days, almost all families made a pilgrimage to Jerusalem on this occasion (Feinberg Vamosh, 2001, 30). Luke (2:41) claims that Jesus' parents surely did so. As we know, Jesus' family was probably quite large. Mark (6:3) mentions four brothers and several sisters. Though some scholars indicate that the term "brothers" was used in ancient Palestine—similarly as well as in many other parts of the world—to denote also cousins in the male and female lineages, but in no way it can be excluded that they were blood brothers. If Jesus' male lineage was from Bethlehem, then other relatives in that city come into the picture. It is even possible that Jesus had some half-brothers there; the already cited Proto-Gospel of James (17: 8) asserts that just before the birth of Jesus, Jesus' parents were accompanied on their way from Nazareth to Bethlehem by Joseph's sons from his earlier marriage. Therefore, it is very likely that in the transfer of Jesus' body to the family tomb in Bethlehem participated some members of Jesus' immediate family.

In such a situation, discovering an empty tomb should not be so surprising, unlike the astonishment of Jesus' followers at finding the empty tomb. There is probably just one explanation for that surprise—apparently Jesus' family did not inform the group of his followers that his body had been transferred to the family tomb. You can guess why this happened. Evangelists report that the relationship between Jesus and his family was very tense (R. E. Brown, 1977, 31-32). According to Matthew 12: 46-50, Mary, Jesus' mother, was a person placed outside the circle of Jesus' followers despite the alleged revelations imparted to her, regarding the extraordinary status of her son. Moreover, the entire family of Jesus did not understand who he was and did not believe in his mission (Mark 3: 19-21, 31-35; Luke 8: 19-21; John 7: 1-9). Mark (3:21; 6: 2-4, 6) and John (7: 5) write that James, Jesus' brother, was skeptical about accepting Jesus as the messiah. The relationship between Jesus' family and his followers must have been just as strained—or even more—as that between Jesus' family and his followers—as those who prevent Jesus from leading the life of an exemplary member of the Jewish family. The death of Jesus introduced an additional,

extremely important factor to these difficult relationships. At that moment, all rights to Jesus' mortal remains were taken over by the family—the believers had to be satisfied only with the memories of the moments spent together with him, i.e. only spiritual experience.

The state of intra-family relations was obviously off the radar in the case when it was necessary to fulfill basic religious obligations, pertaining to the burial of a family member. Due to special circumstances of the case, Jesus' funeral had to be private and domestic, not public. To our times, the only narratives that have survived are those created in the circle of Jesus' followers; we know nothing about the state of consciousness of Jesus' close family in this regard. However, after the funeral, the group of Jesus' followers probably had the opportunity to obtain information about the details of this event in terms of a not-so-great city, which was Jerusalem at that time. And this was certainly such an occasion when James, Jesus' brother, joined the first Christian community in Jerusalem. As one of the leaders of this community, he certainly had to answer questions about the posthumous fate of his big brother's body. It would therefore be very important to establish what the members of the commune actually knew about this.

Chronologically, the earliest recorded mention of this stems from Paul's letter to the Corinthians, dated approximately A.D. 55-60 (Licona, 2008, 242). Paul (1 Cor 15: 3-7) writes quite vaguely that Jesus "rose on the third day." It is puzzling that the author does not provide any details about such a fateful event. The term "third day" may be some kind of an allusion to the discovery of the empty tomb, but why did the apostle not clearly write what he meant? We learn a little more from the next text that has survived to our times. The Gospel of Mark (15: 46-47, 16: 5-6) notes quite generally that the *place* (undefined) where Jesus' body was laid, was empty on Sunday morning. Here, too, one must ask why the evangelist does not give more details on this subject, although a little earlier (15: 42-46) he speaks explicitly of Joseph of Arimathea as the one to mount the burial of Jesus. Nor can we learn anything about this from the Deacon Stephen's speech to the Sanhedrin during his trial, as reported to us in Acts (7: 1-58). In turn, Luke (23: 50-56, 24: 1-12) and Matthew (27: 57-61, 28: 1-8), writing their gospels sometime around AD 80-90 (cf. P. Brown, 2008; Ehrman, 1999), already specify that the empty tomb was the tomb of Joseph of Arimathea, and similar information is given by John about a decade later (19: 38-40, 20: 1-10).

Thus, the question arises—did Paul of Tarsus and the evangelist Mark know the true circumstances surrounding the emptying of Joseph of Arimathea's tomb, and if so, why did they not reveal them? It is impossible to resist the impression that there is some mystery connected with this matter, some taboo as to the details of this event. It seems that if a few years later James, Jesus' brother, shared the information regarding the transfer of Jesus' body to the family tomb, it was only with his most trusted associates, and only on the condition of keeping a secret. This is why both

evangelists Mark and Paul maintain the necessary discretion in this matter.

Fairly simple explanation of the reasons for this secrecy suggests itself. Well, the body of Jesus was by no means officially obtained from the Roman authorities, as the Gospels say, but was ransomed directly from Roman soldiers at the place of execution and buried without the knowledge of neither Roman nor Jewish authorities. That is why discretion in this matter was necessary. It seems that we have a few clues that support this assumption. More recently, Feinberg Vamosh (2001, 35) drew attention to the fact that in Jesus' day, the crucified person was often ransomed by bribing for Roman guards. Of course, this practice could not be admitted (at least as long as it was under the same regime). Therefore, while reporting the matter in the case of Jesus, it was necessary to somehow legitimize obtaining the body from the Romans' hands. Citing the consent obtained from Pilate himself, seemed quite a good solution, all the more so since the prosecutor himself reportedly died shortly after leaving Palestine (cf. Maier, 1971; Taylor, 2006), thus he could not deny it. Also, from the image-oriented side, it looked much better when the body of Jesus was obtained from the highest representative of Rome in Palestine, and not from an ordinary executioner for a bribe. The story of sending a centurion to make sure Jesus was dead (Mark 15: 4) may have served to reassure official factors that the very sentence of death was certainly conducted.

Among others, Kennard (1955, 238) also inclines to the version that the body of Jesus was ransomed from the Romans' hands, however, he believes that Joseph of Arimathea purchased the body of Jesus from Pilate himself. However, this version of events seems less probable. If that had happened, there would have been no need to be discreet in this matter. Meanwhile, the existence of such a secret, apart from the already presented above approach of Christian writers to this issue, is also indicated by several other premises. One of them is, e.g., the very early time of the day when the body of Jesus was taken from Joseph's tomb. According to the already cited consistent accounts of the Evangelists (Matthew 28: 1-8; Mark 16: 1-8; Luke 24: 1-12; John 20: 1-10), in the early morning, at dawn, when the women arrived, there had not been Jesus' body in the tomb. The body, therefore, had been taken earlier, under the cover of night, apparently so that there would be no witnesses of this action. As an aside, it is worth noting that the women claiming that the stone closing the entrance to the tomb had been removed had good reason to say that—it was a private tomb of an extraneous family, so these women had no right to open and explore it on their own. There are other significant leads on this matter. Were those who sought to retrieve Jesus' body really able—as the tradition purports—to communicate so easily and directly with the Judea procurator himself? It seems that for someone from conquered folk, it were not so easy and quick to obtain an audience with such a high rank dignitary; in addition, the room for such a maneuver was significantly limited due to the coming dusk. It also does not seem that such a high dignitary would

at all focus his attention on the fate of a body of a single executed criminal. Rather, it may be argued that the fate of such bodies was left in the hands of the immediate executors, who acted in accordance with Roman customs in this regard, as was the case with the garments torn off Jesus, which simply became the property of the soldiers executing the sentence (Luke 23:34; John 19: 23-25). Carrier (2005, footnote 17) even writes that soldiers usually had a considerable margin of discretion as to how to execute the sentence. In turn, Evans (2005, 195) believes that there was no established practice as to authorize the burial of the crucified and there was a great deal of discretion in this matter. It can also be noticed that, probably at the request of Jesus' relatives and as part of the bribe given to the soldiers, Jesus' death was hastened. He was pierced with a spear (John 19: 31-37), which greatly shortened his passion on the cross, and also made it possible to bury him before the coming Sabbath. In the usual mode, the crucified person could be dying on the cross for several days (Carrier, 2005).

If the information we are talking about was confidential, then what happened that in the 80-90 CE Matthew and Luke are already writing about the empty tomb and its location without fear? Only one momentous event at that time could fundamentally change the situation—the destruction of Jerusalem in 70 CE. Apparently, in a city with not one stone left on another and no one person left there, keeping a secret about the emptiness of the primary grave of Jesus was not so much essential. Still, of course, none of the accounts says anything that would suggest that Jesus' body might have been moved to another location and that would direct the attention of the authorities to the proper tomb.

It is worth noting that the hypothesis presented above explains in a satisfactory way not only the riddle of the empty tomb—it also explains some other puzzling issues. One such issue is raised by Dunn (2003, 837), who noted with surprise that in the early years of Christianity, no site was worshiped as the burial place (even if just temporary) of Jesus. Similarly, Dijkhuizen (2011, 126-127) notes that for over three hundred years the question of the place of Jesus' burial was of little interest to the Christian intellectual and ecclesial elites, despite the fact that, for example, such a matter as the birthplace of Jesus aroused great interest and stimulated the imagination of believers already at the end of the 1st century AD. Also, before St. Helen, the mother of Emperor Constantine the Great, no one had tried to find Jesus' tomb, dig it out and prove that it was indeed empty, or prove that it contained the remains of the deceased. This strongly contrasts, e.g., with the possession of knowledge of James' (Jesus' brother) tomb location (at least until 180 CE). According to the author, this astonishing silence about the tomb of Jesus may suggest two alternative conclusions: either early Christianity really had no knowledge of this matter, or a more or less conscious decision was made not to remember and venerate the tomb so overwhelmingly associated with shame.

Meanwhile, the matter becomes understandable in the light of the hypothesis presented by us. Despite the disclosure of Jesus' empty tomb, the secret of Jesus' final burial location had to be kept even after the destruction of Jerusalem, as the Romans continued to occupy Palestine and, moreover, the era of mass persecution of Christians initiated by Nero in AD 64 had just begun (cf. Hamman, 1971). In these terms, therefore, the actual tomb and remains of Jesus were in danger of profaning and annihilating. Actually, only when Emperor Constantine at the beginning of the 3rd century CE recognized the Christian religion as legal, and shortly thereafter as one supported by the state, the question of Jesus' burial could be fully discussed. As it seems, however, there was no longer anybody who knew the essential details of the case; for example, Hamman (1971) reports that at the beginning of the 2nd century CE the bishop of Jerusalem was already the non-Jewish Mark. Needless to say, the mystery surrounding Jesus' final burial was an excellent breeding ground for the most fanciful theories on this subject.

In this context, another surprising point is very significant. As R. E. Brown (1994, 117) notes, the narrative of Jesus' passion and resurrection was once separate from that of the discovery of an empty tomb. Dunn (2003, 840) thinks similarly:

to some extent the two streams of tradition (empty tomb, resurrection appearances) were independent from each other. Paul could virtually ignore the former; and the earliest accounts of the empty tomb make no mention of any appearance at the tomb itself. This restraint makes it hard to argue that one stream of tradition gave rise to the other. On the contrary, though interdependent in terms of the earliest conceptualization of Jesus' resurrection, the traditions themselves seem to have emerged from and to have kept alive independent memories.

According to (Dunn, 2003, 840) it cannot be maintained that the earliest tradition referred only to the revelation of Jesus after the resurrection, and that the story of the empty tomb is a later legend that serves to prove the already existing belief about the resurrection of Jesus understood in a materialistic way.

This strange twofold narrative also fits well with our hypothesis. As we have already shown, neither Paul nor Mark could write about the emptied tomb of Jesus in Jerusalem without arousing the suspicions of the authorities. In this situation, the hatching Christology of Paul necessarily had to refer only to the revelations experienced—or claimed to have been experienced—by the followers of Jesus and Paul himself. Crossan (1998, 163) believes that the teaching about the resurrection of Jesus begins with Paul (Licona, 2008, 372). On the other hand, the Gospel of Mark (16: 8) contains an account of the discovery of an empty tomb by women, but does not give its location or marking and unexpectedly breaks off at this point, as if the author did not know what was allowed and what was not allowed to say in this case. The (Proto)Christological threads of this

Gospel are also faint and ambiguous. There is only a suggestion that Jesus will appear to his disciples in the near future in Galilee, but there is neither a description of Jesus' resurrection, nor the later revelations of Jesus to his followers (Lowder, 2005). Also, the concept of Jesus' divinity is very poorly marked in this Gospel, if it is present at all—Jesus is treated in it only as a messenger of God (Abruzzi, 2015, 5-6; Fitzmyer, 1970, 135). Despite such enigmatic references to the empty tomb in Paul and Mark, we know that some news about this was circulating in the oral tradition at that time. This is evidenced by the mention of Matthew (28: 11-15) that Christians were accused of stealing Jesus' body at that time. The other evangelists would be able to write in an open text about the location of the empty tomb only after the destruction of Jerusalem, when the tomb itself was already destroyed, along with the entire city. Instead, they develop, to varying degrees and in various forms, the Christology initiated by Paul.

Another confirmation of our hypothesis has to do with one of the most momentous issues troubling early Christianity—its doctrinal and structural diversity. As Abruzzi (2015, 23) writes: "an intense conflict emerged among Christians very shortly after Jesus' death and that this conflict revolved around the very question of who Jesus was and what message he taught". Simon (1972), in turn, writes that Jewish Christians reluctantly related to the interpretation of the Christian doctrine as proposed by Paul of Tarsus. After the destruction of Jerusalem, they lived predominantly in the area east of the Jordan and were almost entirely faithful to the Jewish Scriptures. They regarded Jesus as a fully human being whom God inspired to teach the truth about him and redeem the sins of the world through his death. Judeo-Christians divided themselves into a number of different factions, differing in some details of their doctrine (see also Ehrman, 1999, 2-3, 7, 180-185, 377, 403-404). Abruzzi (2015, 24-25) lists six factions that developed within early Christianity. Among them, two factions, the Nazarenes and Ebionites, were faithful to the Jewish Order (Torah), but while the former believed that Jesus was only a man and a messianic prophet, the latter recognized Jesus as divine. The Ebionites considered Jacob, Jesus' brother, as their leader, while the Nazarenes were initially followers of John the Baptist and only later recognized Jacob's spiritual leadership. And further on the author writes about the Ebionites:

a sect that regarded Jesus as a mortal human messianic prophet but not as a divine being. They insisted on the necessity of following Jewish religious laws and rituals. They also revered Jesus' brother James as the head of the Jerusalem Church (rather than Peter) and rejected Paul of Tarsus as an "apostate of the Law." The Ebionites also rejected the pre-existence, divinity, virgin birth, atoning death and physical resurrection of Jesus.

In turn, Dunn (2002, 577) writes that James and Paul were connoted with two limbs standing on opposite ends of the entire spectrum of stratification in the original doctrinal

Christianity, while Peter served as a bridge between all these trends:

But Peter, as shown particularly by the Antioch episode in Galatians 2, had both a care to hold firm to his Jewish heritage, which Paul lacked, and openness to the demands of developing Christianity, which James lacked.

In this matter, Ehrman (1999, 308) and Abruzzi (2015, 33n6) write quite similarly.

What could be the connection between the doctrinal and structural diversity of early Christianity and the fate of Jesus' body? The point of view of the immediate Jesus' family is extremely important in this last matter—after all, it was the most competent authority and the final depository of knowledge on this subject. Meanwhile, it turns out that very little is known about it. Moreover, we quite unexpectedly note that some Jesus' brothers—let us recall, initially very skeptical of his religious activities—became his followers shortly after his death (1 Cor. 9: 5; Acts 1:14), and one of them, James, became even one of the leaders of the Jerusalem Church (Gal. 1:19; 2: 1-10; Acts 15: 1-21; 21: 17-26). Such a change in mindset of Jesus' family must seem quite mysterious. Early Christian writers tried to use, understandably, the presence of Jesus' family among the original followers of Christianity to authenticate the truths of faith they postulated. For example, Paul (1 Cor 15: 3-7) maintains that among the people to whom Jesus was to appear after his death was also James. This leads some scholars (Fuller, 1980, 37; Spong, 1980, 68) to believe that it was an experience of this kind that was behind James' conversion to Christianity. However, for example, Funk (1998, 454-455) think otherwise, as they do not believe the reports of Jesus' revelation to Jacob. Indeed, the great number of such revelations quoted by Paul and the three Evangelists (Licona, 2008, 221-235) gives the impression that visions of this kind created (at least in the tradition) a *sui generis* "pass" to membership in the newly created religious structures. In fact, it seems that it was quite natural and understandable for some members of Jesus' family to join Christianity even without such miraculous interventions. First, they must have been impressed with willingness to posthumously admire and exalt a member of their lineage; secondly, as the group's strength grew, it was certainly attractive to be able to establish bonds of friendship and solidarity with a large group of people, and to find support among them. It is possible that early followers of Jesus themselves sought the approval and support of Jesus' family members for their movement. There is a well-known tradition in the Middle East that family ties are very positively valued in the field of religious worship. Some scholars believe, in turn, that the martyrdom of James proves his faith in the resurrection of Jesus (Licona, 2008, 319-320). However, the historical circumstances of the case, i.a. the absence of the prosecutor of Judea in the country at that time, the subsequent dismissal of the high priest who sentenced Jacob, the lack of any other persecution of Christians at that time, seem to indicate rather ambitious and political-religious motives in this matter, e.g. the

fear of the Jewish authorities against excessive growth an authority of James the Just, commonly respected and valued by the Jews.

However, it seems that members of Jesus' family certainly played a significant role in the development of the aboriginal Christian community, and the traces of this influence perpetuated for years. Thus the structural and doctrinal differentiation within pristine Christianity could result not only from purely ideological or socio-ethnic premises; it could also reflect a different degree of knowledge about the events related to the posthumous fate of Jesus' body and different attitudes towards such knowledge. The circles best informed on the matter, knowing the truth or a large part of it, were the circles closest to the members of Jesus' family—they are the ones who show far-reaching skepticism about the emerging news of the resurrection and the divine character of Jesus. On the other hand, this kind of news was easily heard among Christian circles remote from the current, prevailing at that time, what especially relates the diaspora areas. Only after some time, for various reasons, those peripheral centers gained such an advantage that they became the core of the new Christian orthodoxy. Thus, a varying degree of familiarization with the facts concerning the posthumous fate of Jesus' body could have had a decisive influence on the shaping of the elements of the Christian faith and the formation of various versions of the Christian doctrine. Thus, from the mythical elements contained in the Christian tradition, through an appropriate reinterpretation, we come to commonly known historical facts.

Bibliography

- Abruzzi, W. S. (2015). The birth of Jesus: A critical analysis of the infancy narratives. Retrieved from http://www.drabruzzo.com/birth_of_jesus.htm
- Allison, D. C. (2005). *Resurrecting Jesus: The earliest Christian tradition and its interpreters*. New York: T&T Clark.
- Borg, M. (1999). The meaning of the birth stories. In M. J. Borg & N. T. Wright (Eds.), *The meaning of Jesus: Two visions*. San Francisco, CA: Harper.
- Bostock, G. (1994). Do we need an Empty Tomb? *The Expository Times*, 105(7), 201-205.
- Breytenbach, C. (2012). Burial: New Testament. In J. Frey, D. Allison, V. Leppin, & C. L. Seow (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of the Bible and its reception* (Vol. 4). Berlin/New York: de Gruyter.
- Brown, P. (2008). *The body and society: Men, women, and sexual renunciation in early Christianity*. New York: Columbia University Press.

- Brown, R. E. (1977). *The birth of the Messiah: A commentary on the infancy narratives in Matthew and Luke*. Garden City, NY: Doubleday.
- Brown, R. E. (1994). *The death of the Messiah: From Gethsemane to the grave: A commentary on the Passion narratives in the four Gospels*. New York: Doubleday.
- Buchanan, G. W. (1984). *Jesus, the king and his kingdom*. Macon, GA: Mercer University Press.
- Carnley, P. (1987). *The structure of resurrection belief*. New York: Clarendon Press - Oxford University Press.
- Carrier, R. C. (2005). The burial of Jesus in light of Jewish Law. In R. M. Price & J. J. Lowder (Eds.), *The empty tomb: Beyond the grave* (pp. 105-231). Amherst, NY: Prometheus Books.
- Cohen-Matlofsky, C. (2013). The imperfect 'Tomb of Jesus and his family'. In *The tomb of Jesus and his family? Exploring ancient Jewish tombs near Jerusalem's walls* (pp. 76-107). Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans.
- Craffert, P. F., & Botha, P. J. (2005). Why Jesus could walk on the sea but he could not read and write: Reflections on historicity and interpretation in historical Jesus research. *Neotestamentica*, 39(1), 5-35.
- Craig, W. L. (1985). The historicity of the empty tomb of Jesus. *New Testament Studies*, 31(01), 39-67.
- Craig, W. L. (1989). *Assessing the New Testament evidence for the historicity of the resurrection of Jesus*. Lewiston, NY: Mellen Press.
- Craig, W. L. (2014). Did Jesus rise from the dead? In M. J. Wilkins & J. P. Moreland (Eds.), *Jesus under fire: Modern scholarship reinvents the historical Jesus* (pp. 147-182). Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan Academic.
- Crossan, J. D. (1996). *Who killed Jesus?: Exposing the roots of anti-Semitism in the gospel story of the death of Jesus*. San Francisco: Harper.
- Crossan, J. D. (1998). *The birth of Christianity: Discovering what happened in the years immediately after the execution of Jesus*. San Francisco: Harper.
- Crossan, J. D., & Reed, J. L. (2001). *Excavating Jesus: Beneath the stones, behind the texts*. San Francisco: Harper.
- Dijkhuizen, P. (2011). Buried shamefully: Historical reconstruction of Jesus' burial and tomb. *Neotestamentica*, 45(1), 115-129.
- Dunn, J. D. G. (2002). Has the Canon a continuing function? In L. M. McDonald & J. A. Sanders (Eds.), *The Canon Debate* (pp. 558-579). Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic.
- Dunn, J. D. G. (2003). *Jesus remembered*. Grand Rapids, MI: W.B. Eerdmans.
- Eddy, P. R., & Boyd, G. A. (2007). *The Jesus legend: A case for the historical reliability of the*

- synoptic Jesus tradition*. Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic.
- Ehrman, B. D. (1999). *Jesus: Apocalyptic prophet of the new millennium*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Evans, C. A. (2005). Jewish burial traditions and the resurrection of Jesus. *Journal for the Study of the Historical Jesus*, 3(2), 233-248.
- Evans, C. A. (2009). The silence of burial. In C. A. Evans & N. T. Wright (Eds.), *Jesus, the final days: What really happened*. Louisville, KY: Westminster John Knox Press.
- Feinberg Vamosh, M. (2001). *Daily life at the time of Jesus*. Nashville, TN: Abingdon Press.
- Fisher, R. (1999). The empty tomb story in Mark: its origin and significance. *Neotestamentica*, 33(1), 59-77.
- Fitzmyer, J. A. (1970). The priority of Mark and the "Q" source in Luke. *Jesus and Man's Hope*, 1, 131-170.
- Freed, E. (2004). *The stories of Jesus' birth*. Sheffield, UK: Sheffield Academic Press.
- Fuller, R. H. (1980). *The formation of the Resurrection narratives*. Philadelphia: Fortress Press.
- Funk, R. W., and the Jesus Seminar. (1998). *The acts of Jesus: What did Jesus really do*. San Francisco: Harper.
- Grant, M. (1977). *Jesus: An historian's review of the Gospels*. New York: Scribner.
- Habermas, G. (2004). The Empty Tomb of Jesus: Recent Critical Arguments. *Lecture given at the Evangelical Philosophical Society (November 2004)*. Retrieved from <https://www.namb.net/apologetics/resource/the-empty-tomb-of-jesus/>
- Hachlili, R. (1988). Jewish ornamental ossuaries of the late Second Temple period *Catalogue, No. 4 (Spring 1988)*, University of Haifa, Israel.
- Hamman, G. A. (1971). *La vie quotidienne des premiers chrétiens (95-197)*. Paris: Hachette.
- Hollenbach, P. W. (1982). The conversion of Jesus: From Jesus the Baptizer to Jesus the Healer. *Aufstieg und Niedergang der römischen Welt, II.25.1*, 196-219.
- Holtzmann, H. (1906). Das leere Grab und die gegenwärtigen Verhandlungen über die Auferstehung Jesu. *Theologische Rundschau*, 9(4), 119-132.
- Kennard, J. S. (1955). The burial of Jesus. *Journal of Biblical Literature*, 74, 227-238.
- Kirby, P. (2005). The case against the empty tomb. In R. M. Price & J. J. Lowder (Eds.), *The empty tomb: Beyond the grave* (pp. 233-260). Amherst, NY: Prometheus Books.
- Klausner, J. (1925). *Jesus of Nazareth; His life, times, and teaching* (H. Danby, Trans.). New York: Macmillan.
- Licona, M. R. (2008). *The historicity of the resurrection of Jesus: historiographical considerations in the light of recent debates*. Doctoral dissertation. University of Pretoria.

- Lowder, J. J. (2005). Historical evidence and the empty tomb story: A replay to William Lane Craig. In R. M. Price & J. J. Lowder (Eds.), *The empty tomb: Beyond the grave* (pp. 261-306). Amherst, NY: Prometheus Books.
- Magness, J. (2007). The burial of Jesus in light of archaeology and the Gospels. *Eretz-Israel: Archaeological, Historical and Geographical Studies*, 1-7. Retrieved from www.jstor.org/stable/23630927.
- Maier, P. L. (1971). The Fate of Pontius Pilate. *Hermes*, 99(3), 362-371.
- Marcus, I. G. (2004). *The Jewish life cycle: Rites of passage from biblical to modern times*. Seattle, WA: University of Washington Press.
- McCane, B. R. (2003). *Roll back the stone: Death and burial in the world of Jesus*. Harrisburg, PA: Trinity Press International.
- McDonald, L. M. (2013). The burial of Jesus in light of Jewish burial practices and Roman crucifixions In J. H. Charlesworth (Ed.), *The tomb of Jesus and his family? Exploring ancient Jewish tombs near Jerusalem's walls* (pp. 76-107). Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans.
- Meier, J. P. (1991). *A marginal Jew: Rethinking the historical Jesus*. New York: Doubleday.
- O'Collins, G., & Kendall, D. (1994). Did Joseph of Arimathea exist? *Biblica*, 75(2), 235-241.
- Pixner, B. (1990). Church of the Apostles found on Mt. Zion. *Biblical Archaeology Review*, 16(3), 16-35.
- Robinson, J. A. T. (1973). *The human face of God*. Philadelphia, PA: Westminster Press.
- Sanders, E. P. (1985). *Jesus and Judaism*. Minneapolis, MN: Fortress Press.
- Sanders, E. P. (1993). *The historical figure of Jesus*. London: Penguin Books.
- Shoemaker, S. J. (2001). The (re?) discovery of the Kathisma Church and the cult of the virgin in late antique Palestine. *Maria*, 1(2), 21-72.
- Shoemaker, S. J. (2003). Christmas in the Qur'an: The Qur'anic account of Jesus' nativity and Palestinian local tradition. *Jerusalem Studies in Arabic and Islam*, 28, 11-39.
- Simon, M. (1972). *La civilisation de l'antiquité et le christianisme*. Paris: Arthaud.
- Spong, J. S. (1980). *The Easter moment*. New York: Seabury Press.
- Taylor, J. E. (2006). Pontius Pilate and the imperial cult in Roman Judaea. *New Testament Studies*, 52(4), 555-582.
- Vermes, G. (2006). *The Nativity: History and legend*. London: Penguin Books.
- Vermes, G. (2008). *The Resurrection: History and myth*. London: Penguin Books.